

MODELING AND SIMULATION OF SLOTTED WAVEGUIDE ANTENNA STIFFENED STRUCTURES

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1. Abstract

This paper is concerned with modeling and simulation of composite waveguide structures. Slotted waveguide antenna stiffened structures (SWASS) were considered with the aim to improve the structural strength and stiffness of an integrated aircraft wing or fuselage, while evaluating radio frequency (RF) performance. For structural analysis, initially a 2D equivalent model approximated the structural failure by using the smeared stiffness method and was verified against an analytical model. The difference between smeared stiffness and classical model was good. Higher fidelity models were indicated by discrepancy between smeared slots and finite element method (FEM). For verification of accuracy, it was compared with results in the literature for a solid FEM model. Recently, four design concepts have been proposed and developed by AFRL. The structural instability of those concepts under uniaxial compressive loading was studied as a realistic application of the 3D plate model. In addition, for reliable and lightweight design, mass efficiency at each design concept is examined. This procedure can be used in design and optimization of efficient waveguide structures.

2. Introduction

Research on conformal load-bearing antenna (CLAS) structures [1] has increased, due to their favorable characteristics like multi-functional integrity of aircraft and antenna structures. In the design of CLAS, both structural strength and electromagnetic (EM) performance are equally important and depend on material and geometry. Callus [2] presented a brief history of the CLAS concept and reviewed various types of antenna-embedded structures. This general concept is

deepened and narrowed into SWASS, which provides results to demonstrate computational modeling of SWASS structures and RF experimental verification.

The continuing work on SWASS has focused on improving structural performance by enhancing robustness and stability. As discussed by Sabat *et al* [3], structural failure and instability problems of SWASS have extensively studied through a single composite rectangular wave guide. Simulation results under uniaxial compressive load have been verified against experiment results.

Kim *et al* [4] suggested an optimum design technique for WR-90 waveguide to maximize the EM performance. The authors investigated trends of radio wave pattern sensitivity by varying slot size, and space and even geometry of the waveguide. Regarding RF performance sensitivity associated with aircraft structure, Smallwood *et al* studied the dipole antenna-embedded structure on joined-wing aircraft [5]. The authors investigated the effect on sensitivity of RF performance due to structural deformation associated with aerodynamic load. To minimize weight and maximize stiffness without degrading EM performance are the main objective of SWASS. Knutsson *et al* tried to find or develop the materials not only to save weight, but also increase electrical properties [6].

In this paper, in the development of minimization of weight and maximization of structural strength, four design concepts of waveguides are proposed. These are composite rectangular waveguide tubes covered by electromagnetically transparent composite laminate skins. Our main objective is to present structural response of four design concepts. In addition, we will suggest effective design criteria for

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mass effective design. Firstly, the 2D approximated modeling was demonstrated for simplified fast prediction. For higher fidelity modeling, 3D plate modeling was proposed. Structural responses were evaluated under uniaxial compression and verified against Sabat's single waveguide model on non-slotted and slotted cases [3]. For practical structural application, mass efficiency at each design concept is examined. These normalized design criteria can be extended to the work that optimizes mass, stiffness and RF performance.

3. Design Concepts of SWASS

Structural analysis and evaluation of four novel design concepts for SWASS, shown in Fig. 1, was carried out. These various composite structures possess a spectrum of performance capabilities characterized by 1) the stability subject to loading conditions, 2) effective mass ratio compared to the metallic reinforcement, and 3) the conductivities to be able to transmit an EM signal. We suggest four design concepts to improve structural responses and EM.

In detail, concept 1 has load-bearing carbon fiber waveguide tubes with carbon-fiber inner and outer

mold line face sheets. This structure is expected to effectively support various loads and as a result, prevent buckling and failure. In addition, due to conductivity of carbon fiber, EM signals can be guided by the fiber tube. Since the carbon fiber face sheets are also electrically conducting, slots must be cut through the top skins, which weaken structural stiffness. Concept 2 is similar to concept 1, except that its face sheet material is fiberglass. Fiberglass is electromagnetically transparent, therefore no additional slots are required on the top skin, which is able to increase structural strength, even though fiberglass is not considered as stiff as carbon fiber.

Concept 3 is different from concept 1 and concept 2 in that it has thin copper metallic foil waveguide tubes to conduct electromagnetic signals. Only the metallic foil waveguide has slots, which has relatively less influences on mechanical strength. Face sheets are fiberglass, which is EM transparent; therefore no additional slots are required through outer skins. Concept 4 is same as concept 3, except for replacing inner mold line (IML) material on the bottom face sheet with carbon fiber in order to increase stiffness.

Fig. 1. Four design concepts of Slotted Waveguide Antenna Stiffened Structures.

4. Equivalent 2D modeling

In this section, the mathematical derivation for 2D equivalent model will be presented. It is analogous to a smeared honeycomb sandwich structure model in that the inherent material properties and geometries are reduced from 3D to 2D. The analytical approach follows the assumption of classical thin plate theory [7] including the first-order shear deformation and is compared to 2D FEM model that may be more comparable to the analytical model. The coordinate and loading condition are illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Configuration of waveguide antenna under uniaxial loading.

4.1 Equivalent modeling of core webs

For model comparison and verification, two configurations of equivalent model are suggested: firstly, equivalent core in Fig. 3(a) and secondly, equivalent beam stiffness in Fig. 3(b). The first configuration smears the web material across a homogenous core, while the second model the core web as beam stiffeners.

Fig. 3. Two configurations of equivalent model

The benefit of these approaches is to simplify the complex 3D composite structure for SWASS such as composite web columns in internal structure or slots on the surface plate into the corresponding 2D plate or 1D beam material problems. Another advantage is to save computational cost. Theoretical results demonstrate the accuracy and establish a guideline for suitability of an equivalent model.

4.2 Mathematical formulation

The general expression for 2D equivalent plate model is derived from the principal virtual work problem [8, 9].

$$\delta U + \delta V = \delta \Pi = 0 \quad (1)$$

where $U + V = \Pi$ is the total potential energy, δU the virtual strain energy, δV the virtual work done applied forces. Specifically, the virtual strain energy (δU) is written as

$$\delta U = \int_V \left[\sigma_{xx} \delta \epsilon_{xx} + \sigma_{yy} \delta \epsilon_{yy} + 2\sigma_{yz} \delta \gamma_{yz} + 2\sigma_{xz} \delta \gamma_{xz} + 2\sigma_{xy} \delta \gamma_{xy} \right] dV \quad (2)$$

For 2D modeling, the cross section of waveguide structures can be divided into three parts: top and bottom face sheets and web core in the middle. It is assumed that top and bottom skins support axial and bending/shear loads. And those can be easily modeled as thin plates. The web core improves structural responses by increasing stiffness. For simplicity, suppose that the web core mainly supports transverse shear and x-directional normal stresses. Hence, stress components distributed over the cross-sectional area can be expressed in terms of face sheets and equivalent web core. The simply modified equation is summarized as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \sigma_{yz} \\ \sigma_{xz} \\ \sigma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \sigma_{yz} \\ \sigma_{xz} \\ \sigma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}_{laminates} + \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \sigma_{xz} \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}_{equiv} \quad (3)$$

Classical laminate plate theory dictates that the strain components can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}\varepsilon_{xx} &= \varepsilon_{xx}^0 + z\kappa_x, \quad \varepsilon_{yy} = \varepsilon_{yy}^0 + z\kappa_y, \quad \varepsilon_{yz} = \varepsilon_{yz}^0, \\ \varepsilon_{xz} &= \varepsilon_{xz}^0, \quad \varepsilon_{xy} = \varepsilon_{xy}^0 + z\kappa_{xy}\end{aligned}\quad (4)$$

where κ_x , κ_y and κ_{xy} are given by

$$\kappa_x = -\frac{\partial\phi_x}{\partial x}, \quad \kappa_y = -\frac{\partial\phi_y}{\partial y}, \quad \kappa_{xy} = -\left(\frac{\partial\phi_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial\phi_y}{\partial x}\right) \quad (5)$$

The derivation of the constitutive relationship for stress and strain may be found in [9]. The rule of thumb is that each laminate skin is assumed to be in a state of plane stress, i.e., the normal stresses along z-direction are zero. The layers are assumed to be perfectly bonded together and linearly deform normal to the mid-plane. By substituting Equations (3) and (4) into (2) in conjunction with the in-plane force and moment resultants, the in-plane stiffness matrix [A], the in-plane and out-of plane coupling stiffness [B], and the bending stiffness matrix [D] are expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}A_{ij} &= \sum_{k=1}^{N_k} (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k (z_k - z_{k-1}) + A_{web,equiv} \\ B_{ij} &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{N_k} (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k (z_k^2 - z_{k-1}^2) + B_{web,equiv} \\ D_{ij} &= \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=1}^{N_k} (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k (z_k^3 - z_{k-1}^3) + D_{web,equiv}\end{aligned}\quad (6)$$

$i, j = 1, 2$ and 6

where N_k is total number of laminate layers, z_k, z_{k-1} are the distance from the reference plane to the two surfaces of k^{th} layer and \bar{Q}_{ij} is the element of the stiffness matrix. A set of equivalent web core stiffness matrices, $A_{web,equiv}$, $B_{web,equiv}$ and $D_{web,equiv}$, are calculated through the two methods. The details are shown in the following sections. For transverse shear stiffness matrix,

$$K_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^N (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k (z_k - z_{k-1}), \quad i, j = 4 \text{ and } 5 \quad (7)$$

The explicit expression for the transverse shear stiffness can be computed as strain energy balance under the assumption of the first-order deformation.

4.2.1 Equivalent core: Volume Fraction Approach

We assume that load is evenly distributed in the web core so that stiffness can be smeared across single plate layer models. The equivalent material properties of Young's modulus (E^*) and shear modulus (G^*) can be expressed in terms of volume fraction (α).

$$E^* = \alpha E, \quad \alpha = \frac{V_{ns} - V_s}{V_{ns}} \quad (8)$$

$$G^* = \alpha G$$

where E is the Young's modulus, G is the shear modulus, V_{ns} is the total volume of the internal core structure space, V_s is the total volume of web columns. Therefore, all of the three equivalent stiffness matrices, $A_{web,equiv}$, $B_{web,equiv}$ and $D_{web,equiv}$, are computed with single plate layer.

4.2.2 Equivalent beam

In the second model, the shear webs were modeled as beams to carry concentrated in-plane and shear loads. From Timoshenko-beam theory, the coupled governing equation is given by

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\kappa^2 AG \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} - \psi \right) \right] + p &= 0 \\ D \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} + \kappa^2 AG \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} - \psi \right) &= 0\end{aligned}\quad (9)$$

where $w = w(x)$ is the transverse deflection, $\psi = \psi(x)$ is the bending slope, κ^2 is the shape factor, G is the shear modulus, $p = p(x)$ is externally applied force along the length of the beam, D is the bending stiffness. In this approach, the coupling matrix, $B_{web,equiv}$, is disregarded, since the neutral axis of beam stiffeners is set to the location of the neutral plane of the plates. Therefore, $A_{web,equiv}$ and $D_{web,equiv}$ are decoupled and modeled as beams.

4.3 Model verification

In order to verify the accuracy of the equivalent smeared stiffness approach, FEM modeling was performed in order to see the correlation with analytical approximation for concept 1. Note that length, a , and width, b , are ten times greater than height, h for thin plate model. The NASTRAN-based FEMAP software [10] was used to model the composite layers with the equivalent core structures. The QUAD4 shell elements were used for the laminate skin plates [11]. The detailed material properties are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Material properties [9].

	CFRP	Glass Fiber	Copper
$E1(\times 10^6 \text{ psi})$	20.1	7.8	18.0
$E2(\times 10^6 \text{ psi})$	1.2	2.6	18.0
$G12(\times 10^6 \text{ psi})$	0.6	1.3	6.72
$G23(\times 10^6 \text{ psi})$	0.72	0.5	6.72
$G13(\times 10^6 \text{ psi})$	0.72	1.3	6.72
ν_{12}	0.26	0.25	0.34
$\rho \text{ (lb/in}^3\text{)}$	0.0659	0.0686	0.322

Fig. 4 demonstrates the non-dimensional buckling load of the equivalent model along with theoretical results as a function of aspect ratio ($a/b = \text{length/width}$) under compressive uniaxial load with four simply supported edges. As can be seen in Fig. 4, the two equivalent configurations, which are equivalent core and equivalent beam stiffeners, are well matched. However, there are differences between equivalent models and classical plate theory. Fig. 5 depicts trend of change of buckling load under consideration of slot size effect. The value of figure of merit of normalized buckling loads has been plotted as a function of Volume Fraction Factor (α). It is easily observed from both equivalent models that as the volume of slots increase, because of the reduction of equivalent stiffness, the nominal buckling loads decreases. However, there are significant difference between equivalent model and slots modeled as mesh (FEM) at $\alpha=0.9$. Clearly, there is still considerable work to be done in modifying this approach for structural evaluation and verification with three-dimensional approach which generally has higher fidelity.

Fig. 4. Comparison of volume fraction method and theoretical approach without slots.

Fig. 5. Slot volume fraction effect:

5. Discussion of Results for 3D Plate Model

The buckling response of a 3D plate model was evaluated through comparison with a previous model studied by Sabat [3] and extended to the application of four design concepts.

5.1 Model verification of 3D plate FEM model

It is worthy to investigate our proposed 3D plate model by comparing with previous work that simulates a single rectangular tube CFRP composite structure [3].

Table 2 shows the simulation result of the critical buckling load for non-slotted and slotted waveguide tubes. As can be seen from the table, the difference of simulation results of buckling between Sabat's and 3D plate models is less than 3%. The 3D plate

model matched Sabat's 3D solid model well, whereas the 3D plate model has significantly fewer number of elements than Sabat's solid model. The important conclusion to draw from the table is that the 3D plate model is more efficient than Sabat's model, since it saves computation cost and is relatively accurate. However, neither simulation results match experimental results well. Further investigation is required to explain the discrepancy.

Table 2. Comparison of structural instability between Sabat's and 3D plate models.

	Exp. [3]	Sabat [3]	3D plate
Non-slotted (1 st mode)	730.0	938.7 (28.6%)	928.9 (27.4%)
Slotted (1 st mode)	640.0	863.3 (35%)	892.2 (39.4%)
# of Elements	N/A	40,000 (Approx.)	1,000 (Approx.)

Note: () is difference between FEM and experiment:
 $(FEM - Exp.) / Exp \times 100 (\%)$.

5.2 Structural instability of four design concepts of SWASS

AFRL recently provided four novel design concepts of SWASS for parameterization with varying panel dimensions and boundary conditions for prediction of buckling and failure.

Fig. 6 shows the buckling comparison of a 3D plate model for the multiple-tube slotted waveguide structures. These are three-tube slotted waveguides with simply supported (SS) and clamped-clamped (CC) boundary conditions on both ends, under distributed uniaxial load on the cross-section of the waveguide tube. Critical buckling is normalized by the 1st global buckling of concept 1 with the SS boundary condition. The SS boundary condition on both ends may not be realistic, but is useful as a lower bound for a more conservative buckling load than the CC boundary condition on both ends. The local buckling loads are approximately 1.5 times higher when slotted waveguides are designed with thin metallic foil tube with fiber skins (concept 3 and concept 4). Concepts 1 and 2, which have a carbon fiber tube with composite laminate skins, in contrast, have a low critical buckling load.

Fig. 6. Buckling response of three-tube slotted waveguides. Normalized buckling factor is buckling factor/(1st global buckling factor (SS) at concept1).

Contour plots of buckling mode shapes deformation are shown in Fig. 7. The transverse deflection pattern of the SS case looks like Euler beam-column behavior: a half sinusoid wave as shown Fig. 7(a). But, another pattern of the deflections of the CC are illustrated in Fig. 7(b). Many sinusoidal waves are seen in top face sheet layers (we call it a local mode) that are structurally weakened by slots. One interesting result is shown in Fig. 7(c) where local buckling was found at the bottom panel in concept 4, rather than on top, even though top face sheet layers are considered to be softer stiffness. This indicates that bottom face sheet layers more carry load when the uniaxial load is applied, and resulted in their buckling first.

Fig. 7. Contour of buckling mode shapes.

The consideration of mass effect is substantial for lightweight design. Another plot of the non-dimensional, uniaxial buckling load normalized by mass for the four waveguide concepts is shown in Fig. 8. On the vertical axis, the mass-normalized buckling load is plotted where normalized buckling factor is divided by the normalized mass of concept 1. Three curves are shown, corresponding to the normalized buckling factors in Fig. 6. These are similar to those of Fig. 6. Most importantly, however, this figure provides insight into buckling variation over mass ratio and provides a lightweight design criterion. In local buckling, the thin metallic foil composite waveguides have high stiffness, as well as mass efficiency, even though they are composed of metal foil having high mass density. For global buckling, concept 1 has good mass efficiency, since it is a composite structure and the lightest of all four concepts.

Fig. 8. Mass-normalized buckling of three-tube slotted waveguides. Normalized BF = Buckling factor/(1st global buckling factor(SS) at concept1). Normalized Mass = mass at each concept/(Mass at concept1)

6. Conclusions and Future Work

This research presents modeling and analysis of the four novel SWASS design concepts. The waveguide core tubes, which consist of electromagnetically conducting composite or metallic materials, are expected to be strengthened by top and bottom face sheet laminates. The equivalent model was proposed and compared to an analytical approach. This method is important in that it is cost-effective by simplifying 3D structure into 2D plate model to indicate rough trends, but also leads to substantial approximation error when smearing the effect of

slots. For higher fidelity, 3D plate FEM models for these structures are proposed to evaluate the mechanical failure and lightweight design criteria. The results of this study indicate that the metallic foil waveguides have higher stiffness as well as mass efficiency.

For future work, our study will be extended to optimization in design as well as nonlinear structural analysis. Furthermore, nonlinear structural analysis will provide parameters for a wider range of design criteria of the waveguide structures.

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